

On the road to standardization in Microfluidics and Organ-on-Chip

Henne van Heeren (enablingMNT), Vania Silverio (INESC MN Microsistemas e Nanotecnologias), Elsa Batista (IPQ), Darwin R. Reyes (NIST)

Version 2

11-3-2024

10.5281/zenodo.10804999

Contact: henne@enablingMNT.com

This report contains the authors' impressions from the workshop and does not claim to be the official point of view of any of the attendees.

Workshop Background and Goal (MFMET, MFA, Survey)

This report presents the results of a two-day workshop aimed at identifying and prioritising the needs for standards and metrology in the fields of Microfluidics and Organ-on-Chip (OoC)/Microphysiological Systems (MPS). The workshop was co-organised by the Microfluidics Association (MFA) and the European project MFMET.¹ The workshop was hosted by CETIAT, the National Metrology Institute for Flow in France. In preparation for the meeting, a survey was conducted with microfluidics and OoC/MPS experts.

Workshop Facts (number and background of attendees)

The workshop was attended by 45 participants from 10 countries and 3 continents (Europe, America and Asia). Fourteen (14) oral presentations were given by experts from organisations working on metrology, regulation, and microfluidics and OoC/MPS product development, as well as from the semiconductor industry. Some of the presentations covered ongoing initiatives in the fields of standardization and metrology related to the MFMET project.

Each round of presentations, focusing on a specific topic, was followed by a round table. These round tables served as a forum to discuss the specific topic of the session and gather information from the stakeholders regarding the needs, trends, and future expectations in those areas.

Ongoing initiatives on standards and metrology for Microfluidics and OoC

MFMET Activities

The MFMET project aims to contribute to the development of globally accepted standards for microfluidics and to disseminate them to end users in industry (e.g., health and pharmaceutical sectors) and academia. Specifically, the MFMET is developing consensus-based measurement protocols and guidelines. In addition, it is disseminating metrology standards towards normative committees, industry, and end users. The project members are engaged in standardization activities through their participation in ISO TC48/WG3 and the CEN/CENELEC Organ-on-Chip Focus Group (FGOOC). They have also contributed, along with MFA members, to the development of ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics Vocabulary and ISO/CD/TS 6417 - Microfluidic pumps, symbols, and performance communication. Furthermore, they have contributed to several recently published whitepapers on metrology protocols for properties relevant to microfluidics such as leakage, wettability, volume, surface roughness, and more.

This year, metrology experts from different organisations who are partners in the project started addressing the traceability of parameters such as flow, flow resistivity, volume, channel dimensions, and roughness. For this, transfer standards/round robins, based on polymer and glass, were created to be tested on several flow-related properties (e.g., flow resistivity, leakage, dimensions channels, surface roughness) at different locations in Europe and the USA. These transfer standards will serve as a representation of what is needed to characterise and standardise microfluidic devices and will ensure traceability to the key flow control-related quantities.

¹ This project (20NRM02 MFMET) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Figure 1: Design of two of the created transfer standards.

Several of these transfer standards are currently being tested in different labs around the world.

A recent initiative of the MFMET is to develop guidelines for future standardization of modular assembly of the different components (e.g., sensors) in a system through accurate measurements of their dimensions. For this, a series of discussions were held among microfluidic suppliers to come to an agreement about the standardization of the connection/integration of sensors and microfluidic circuits. It was agreed that such a standard connector should facilitate its use with devices that operate in the hot spot of microfluidics (i.e., near room temperature, low pressures and with fluids containing biomolecular matter)². The requirements for the hot spot area in microfluidics include:

- Pressures of up to 200 kPa (2 bars) and temperatures between (4 to 50) °C.
- Suitability of flows between 1 µL/min and 100 µL/min.
- Feasibility of use with water-based fluids containing biomolecular matter.
- Low internal volume, low flow resistivity, limiting risk of biofilm formation
- Biocompatible materials as wetted materials³
- Materials used should be affordable and should have a well-developed supply chain
- Reusable/cleanable/(preferably sterilizable)

² A big area in microfluidics where the devices work under similar conditions. That means that suppliers of microfluidic devices and components can address a large group of users with one version of their product.

³ Wetted materials is a reference to the sub-components of the sensor that are in contact with the process media. These materials should be considered based on their chemical resistance, biological impact and compliance with regulatory specification.

- Leakage free – a good example regarding guidelines to measure leakage can be found in *Overcoming technological barriers in microfluidics: Leakage testing*, Silverio et al. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 2022, 10, 958582.
- Suitable for rigid 1.6 mm (1/16”) outer diameter (OD) tubing (preferably flexible for inner diameter (ID) size, and soft wall tubing too).
- “One click fastening”, no need for special tooling.
- Lowest “footprint” possible/not bulky.
- Design is freely available but fixed in a standard.
- Pathway to further integration.
- Compatibility with *ISO 22916:2022 Microfluidic devices — Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections, and initial device classification*.

The group also identified key aspects of microfluidic connectors that would ensure proper functioning. Those key aspects include:

- No leakage under normal operational conditions.
- Safety margin for pressure.
- Low dead volume.
- Low flow resistivity.
- Good mechanical fixture of the tube.
- Aspects related to biocompatibility, cytotoxicity.
- Chemical resistance, wettability.

For all these key aspects metrology protocols are needed.

A conceptual design of such a standard sensor interface was proposed and accepted by the companies participating in the discussions. It might be transferred into a standard in a later stage. Beginning next year, the discussion will start on future generations of this interface, suitable for other market segments, for which a draft roadmap was proposed.

Suggestions for the standard microfluidic connector roadmap

Figure 2: First suggestion for a microfluidic connector roadmap.

The FMET project operates in cooperation with the Microfluidics Association (MFA) and its members. The MFA was founded by a group of organizations working in the field of microfluidics. The association brings interested parties together to initiate and follow up on actions to promote the microfluidics industry. The MFA has published several guidelines for microfluidics design and fabrication and is also developing more elaborate guidelines and standards during their workshops and in the MFA supported standardization activities. When appropriate, the results will be fed into the ISO TC 48/WG 3 – Microfluidic devices to be used for standards development.

CEN-CENELEC FGOOC Activities

The CEN-CENELEC FGOOC is drafting a roadmap for standardization in organ-on-chip and several members of the MFA and FMET are involved. The following topics will be addressed in this roadmap:

- Terminology, ecosystem, interdependencies.
- Biosciences.
- Engineering.
- Experimental design and data management.
- User perspective and regulatory, legal and ethical aspects.

Recently a second draft of the roadmap has been created; a final version is expected to be published in the summer of 2024.

Activities in Japan

There is substantial interest in Japan for standardization of OoC/MPS; the Japan Bio Measurement & Analysis Consortium (JMAC) is leading the activities. JMAC has strong relations with several

related ISO Technical Committees and Japanese pharma companies. Materials and their processing are focal points. One activity has been to develop a platform for the validation of cell culture technologies and the development of protocol standards. JMAC is now organizing a new project entitled “MF4MPS” (Microfluidics for MPS) focusing on standardization of OoC/MPS including microfluidics-based devices.

Regarding the evaluation criteria for materials, the following properties are in consideration:

- Processability.
- Autofluorescence strength.
- Impact resistance (a combination of an object’s strength (how easily it breaks) and ductility (how easily it deforms)).
- Optical access.
- Oxygen permeability.

JMAC considers ISO 22916 Microfluidic devices Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections and initial device classification to also be a good basis to design test specimens for Microfluidics Material Evaluation.

US FDA Perspective on Standards

According to the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), standards take a long time to gain consensus and are often not approved until the particular medical device category is well-established, which means that early developers have to do a lot of the heavy lifting.

The FDA’s Regulatory Science Tool (RST) is an innovative, science-based approach or methodology to help assess the safety or effectiveness of a medical device or emerging technology. These provide resources for companies and reviewers to use where standards and Medical Device Development Tools (MDDTs) do not yet exist. (see next figure)

Figure 3: Regulatory Science Tool can be used when standards are not yet available.

Regulatory Science Tools do not replace FDA-recognized standards. Regulatory Science Tools reduce the need for device developers to design ad-hoc test methods and allow them to focus their

limited resources on how well their new product works, not how well it may be tested. These tools represent an important contribution to reducing risk in all stages of product development and are particularly important to the early inventors and innovators, who often don't have means to evaluate their systems.

Types of challenges identified by the FDA in the translation of microfluidics-based medical devices are:

- Sample loading.
- Sensing / assays.
- Flow.
- Analysis.
- Mechanical integrity.
- Materials / design / fabrication.
- Failure modes.
- Errors.
- Interconnections / accessories.

Other remarks made during the meeting

Remarks related to flow control

- Establishment of consensus-based flow control specifications for microfluidics components and devices is an important part of the work to democratize microfluidics. Currently, the selection of the most suitable microfluidic devices and components is hindered by the lack of sufficient information supplied by manufacturers/suppliers. In a first attempt to mitigate this need, MFMET partners prepared a database for flow control components for microfluidics, available to the public. This database contains flow characteristics (e.g., range, accuracy) and mechanical characteristics (e.g., pressure range, and connections type and size).
- Topics to be addressed are: ways to describe the response to changing flow rates, an essential piece of information for running sensitive biological tests; symbols for pumps, vocabulary, etc. Several key performance parameters and topics that have major influence on flow accuracy have been identified for future metrology protocol development. Traditional methods for leakage testing are not suitable for microfluidic devices as they are either destructive, work with other media than the media used by the users (for instance, gas instead of liquid), are not practical in an industrial setting, or are not accurate enough. Currently, work is ongoing on how to adapt existing methodologies for flow control used at the macro level to make them suitable for microfluidics.
- There is a lot of interest from industry experts regarding anything that affects pressure drop and flow resistance in a device. There are many aspects to that, but as a priority in metrology around flow rate, flow resistivity and internal volumes are addressed. Several methods are compared in order to obtain reliable and accurate testing protocols.

Remarks related to biological applications

- Biomarkers: there is a huge diversity, and many are application specific. They will likely be measured offline instead of within the microfluidic network. For this to work, compatibility with the microwell plate workflow is important.
- The use of ISO 22916:2022- Microfluidic devices – Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections and initial devices classification in on-going multi-partner research projects on Organ-on-Chip has shown that it helps to ensure compatibility between products from different facilities.

Remarks related to compatibility of components, test protocols and supply chain

1. For a manufacturer of microfluidic devices, inline measurements to control product quality is key. The MFMET project had identified key aspects and quantities to be measured and the tools to perform such measurements.
2. All present suppliers stressed the need for standards to ensure compatibility between components from different suppliers and, in turn, increase reproducibility.
3. Surface characterization should be one of the focal points for further work: understanding and controlling surface properties and how the liquid interaction affects the control of flow rates in small channels are key points.
4. The question was raised about the possibility of developing accelerated test protocols for microfluidic devices.
5. The medium in OoC devices is far from pure water, therefore, it might be useful to define a reference test fluid to be used for validations.
6. Calibration is easier when one uses off the shelf components, underpinning the advantages of modular approaches.

7. There might be a need to define a Technology Readiness Level - like system dedicated to OoC devices/models. This might help to clarify the status of developed OoC devices.
8. Semiconductor companies struggle with the challenge of combining silicon sensors with microfluidics. The options to adapt the silicon processes to facilitate this combination are limited. That implies that most of the development work will be done by the microfluidics community as they have more flexibility in the technology. New approaches and more research are needed.

A particular situation was discussed where a connector that did not show leakage when visually inspected, introduced bacterial contamination to the system during use.

Survey results

An ongoing survey on “Measurement and standardization priorities” has already received 175 responses. The responses clearly identified the top standardization priorities of the interested parties/stakeholders (see next figure):

- Integration of sensors and other microfluidic components.
- Connection to tubes.
- Biocompatibility guidelines.
- Metrology.
- Sterilization guidelines.

Figure 4: Priorities for microfluidic standardization.

In terms of metrology, the top four priorities consist of topics related to microfluidic reliability, i.e., reliability regarding minimization of: leakage at the interfaces of two materials (e.g., bonding strength), at the connection site (between connectors and interfaces), and droplet/bubble presence. These priorities were followed by topics related to manufacturing design and performance. For example, topics of interest were flow rate/flow resistance, dead volume, total internal volume, coating quality, optical transmission/auto fluorescence of polymer materials.

Figure 5: Metrology priorities for Organ-on-Chip and Microfluidics.

One of the attendees referred to a study among researchers. According to this study the main reasons for the lack of adoption of OoC are:

1. Too complicated.
2. No facilities and knowledge to implement it.
3. High costs.
4. No suitable ready-to-use devices.

Other observations from the workshop:

1. Commercially available options are not conceived or designed for perfusion.
2. Importance of real-time sensing of oxygen.
3. Control of shear stress is often essential, underpinning the need for flow control on a miniature scale.
4. Iterations with beta users are important pathways to improve OoC and microfluidic devices.
5. Healthcare is moving and changing fast and shifting towards personalized medicine and Point-of-Care/Need. This transition requires more, better, faster, reliable, easy-to-use and standardized tools and products. Standardization and interoperability will greatly improve the speed of design and development.
6. Organ-on-Chip applications need system reliability particularly because they often need to run for weeks. Therefore, standardization is key as well.

7. Designs should support simple loading and removal of samples/media, and should also provide optical access, enabling high-content imaging with minimal optical aberration with a flat and highly transparent window. There are three important and critical handling steps:
 - Initial liquid loading.
 - Cell/tissue loading into the system.
 - Making fluid connections.
8. There is a need to maintain compatibility with existing workflows (automation and robotics) based on (standard) well plates.
9. Standardization starts at the bottom level: materials, integration and microfluidics.
10. Calibration of sensors is easier with off the shelf components.
11. There are concerns about contamination through connectors.
12. Getting into the microfluidics field is still a hurdle for newcomers.
13. The available standards for biocompatibility are not suited for OoC; not even those for implantable devices.
14. Regulatory science tools are a low-key first step toward a standard.
15. How to link technology standards to regulatory standards?

Validation is the process by which the reliability and relevance of a particular approach, method, process or assessment is established for a defined purpose. For Organ-on-Chip, scientific articles are an element in the process of establishing credibility for a methodology. Therefore, standards to ensure scientific quality for research papers are needed. A good start is: Promoting Reusable and Open Methods and Protocols (PROMaP) and drafting recommendations to improve methodological clarity in life sciences publications. Best practices are highly important, as for example:

- Following guidance document on Good In Vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP).
- Following Good Cell Culture Practice (GCCP).
- Taking care of the calibration and maintenance of equipment.
- Following Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs).

There are many more helpful whitepapers and publications. Several companies provide very instructive information about the basics of microfluidics.

Conclusion and action items

Some general conclusions from the workshop:

- There is a large number of metrology and reliability topics that need to be addressed, thus underpinning the need for cross-organisation, cross-country and even cross-continent cooperation between the interested parties. A first step should be to create a European Metrology Network to connect several initiatives. Also, the cooperation between entities working on standardization around the world could be improved in order not to duplicate work.
- Several topics can only be adequately addressed by in-depth research but current project calls seldom lead to publications addressing failure modes and best practices. This is unfortunate because a good analysis of Failure Modes could lead to improvement of the design/protocol.
- Final product testing needs standardized test protocols.
- Training on the use of microfluidic devices could help non-microfluidics experts to use microfluidic devices effectively.
- Data available must be shared!
- Development of more standards for microfluidics and OoC should be developed in cooperation with TC 48, FGoOC and JMAC.

Identified challenges, focal points for standardization and further discussion

Material properties

- Absorption/adsorption.
- Surface properties; having an effect on:
 - flow resistance,
 - fouling.
 - long-term biocompatibility; cytotoxicity and “normal” biocompatibility are good starting points.
- Could surface modification play a role?
- Moving away from products with auto fluorescence.
- Processability.
- Autofluorescence strength.
- Impact resistance.
- Transparency.
- Oxygen permeability.

Assembly/integration/fabrication/handling

- Manipulation (cleaning, contamination, reuse, sample loading).
- Component's liability/reliability.
- Sensor integration (create a list of types of sensors).
- Mechanical integrity.
- Specification of products.
- Compatibility of different products, sensors, tubes.
- Generic sensors: O₂, CO₂, lactate, glucose, pH: real time measurement, integrated with standard interface.
- Semiconductor chip integration.
- Optical window specification.
- Ease of use/simplicity.
- Connections, assembly, integration, modular set up.

- Suppliers' information (materials and devices/components).
- Incubator suitability (for instance the ability of devices to work under high humidity).

Identified challenges and focal points for metrology

- Media (e.g., liquid or gas) properties.
- Problems associated with the measurements of the inside of channels (dimensions, roughness, impact, etc.).
- Characterization of passive systems. What to report as a supplier and how to measure/qualify them?
- Detection/sensors; calibration of sensors at sensor level or system level?
- Reliability:
 - leakage,
 - relation between air leakage, liquid leakage and contamination leakage,
 - connector reliability,
 - presence of bubbles,
 - dead volume,
 - clogging,
 - contamination,
 - bonding strength,
 - failure modes,
 - are accelerated tests possible? Such tests would speed up the development of devices.
- Other:
 - total internal volume,
 - coating quality,
 - shear stress,
 - optical transmission/auto fluorescence of polymer materials.

Topics for further workshop discussions

- Training.
- Standardized test fluids.
- Transfer standards/round robins,
- Reproducibility of OoC devices.
- GMP (Good Manufacturing Practices).
- What needs to be reported in a scientific paper to make it suitable for creating scientific credibility?
- Transferring the knowledge to standards and later to regulation.

For a summary of ongoing and planned metrology and standardization activities for microfluidics and OoC, see Table 1 (below).

Table 1: Overview of planned metrology and standardization activities for microfluidics and OoC.

Topics	List of issues	Leading organisations	Organizations involved	Start date
Sensor interface	requirements, conceptual design, optical window, key performance parameters, metrology	MFA	MFMET, ISO/TC 48/WG 3	ongoing
Recommendations to improve methodological clarity in life sciences publications. Best practices are of high importance.		?		
Leakage testing	Whitepaper, testing methodology with transfer standard, updated whitepaper	MFMET	MFA, ISO/TC 48/WG 3	ongoing
Wettability testing		MFMET	ISO/TC 48/WG 3	ongoing
Material properties	Processability, autofluorescence strength, impact resistance, transparency, oxygen permeability	JMAC		2024?
Regulatory Science Tools		FDA		ongoing
Design / manufacturing related properties	Bonding strength, dead volume, total volume, coating quality, optical transmission	ISO/TC 48/WG3	MFMET	ongoing
Flow related properties	Flow rate, flow resistivity, liquid properties	MFMET	ISO/TC 48/WG 3	ongoing
Several OoC challenges	Sample Loading, Sensing, Assays, Flow, Analysis, Mechanical Integrity, Materials, Design / Fabrication, Failure Modes / Errors, Interconnections / Accessories	FDA		In process ?
OoC roadmap	Terminology, ecosystem, interdependencies, Biosciences, Engineering, Experimental design and data management, User perspective and regulatory, legal and ethical aspects.	CEN/CENELEC Focus Group on Organ-on-Chip	MFMET and MFA experts	ongoing